

Research on the Impact of Organizational Commitment on Job Satisfaction Between China and Congo-Brazzaville

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to compare the impact of organizational commitment on job satisfaction between China and Congo Brazzaville. First the basis of literature review about job satisfaction, factors affecting job satisfaction, then the analysis part where organizational commitment, Component of organizational commitment are describe and analyzed clearly. Second the model is established and the key condition organizations in China and Congo Brazzaville are clearly detailed. Third a questionnaire is designed, multiplied and distributed in China and Congo. The result of those questionnaires were collected and analyzed by using SPSS. In conclusion the analysis shows that organizational commitment is stronger in China than in Congo at last, some suggestions are made to improve organizational commitment in Congo.

Keywords: Organizational commitment; Components of Organizational commitment; Human Resource; Job satisfaction; Employee commitment characteristic.

1. Introduction

Organizational commitment has been the subject of numerous researches over the last 30 years. Practitioners and theorists, in industrial relations, economics, management, psychology and sociology have focused on the study of the concept, whose (Becker 1960, Mowday, Steers & Porter 1982, Allen & Meyer 1990, Mueller, Wallace & Price 1992). Nowadays with the evolution of human resource management models and changes in the organization of work, the attention brought to the concept has accentuated and allowed to examine the relationship it has with certain factors, on one hand such as education, seniority and on the other hand on the organizational life especially on satisfaction at work, absenteeism, performance (Mowday, Steer & Porter, 1982; Sommer, Bae & Luthans 1996). Thus studies related to those subjects suggest that organizational commitment explain some behaviors of employees in the organizational area. For instance employees having high degree of commitment in a certain organization would perform better and be more productive (Meyer & Allen, Paunonen, Goffin & Jackson 1989) and would less think of leaving the organization. Some other author as (Wiener, Muczyk & Gable 1987) went a bit further by affirming that employees that have high degree of commitment into the organization would feel a high wellbeing. Once employees have positive attitude towards the works they are currently occupying, that drives to a relationship with the job performance. When they tend to leave the job when their skills, talents are not properly developed or when the managers fail to promote their career development, they are unsatisfied with the boss or management (Hay, 2001). All this reasons show how satisfied employees can be with their jobs. There are essentially two types of job satisfaction based on the level of employees' feelings regarding their jobs, the most analyzed, is global job satisfaction, which refers to employees' overall feelings about their jobs.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Job satisfaction

Job satisfaction is the most widely researched job attitude and was considered one of the key variables in the relationship of the human being and the organization since the Hawthorne studies (Roetlisberger & Dickson, 1939).

Factors such as productivity, commitment or voluntary turn-over as well as determinants as leeway for decision-making and executing tasks, have been more analyzed since then. Job satisfaction is a positive attitude or emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experience. When those attitudes towards the job are positive, it's illustrating the job satisfaction but when the attitudes towards the job are negative, it does illustrate job dissatisfaction (Armstrong, 2006).

2.1.1 Dimension of job Satisfaction

According to Locke (1976) it's difficult to understand the job attitudes, it's better to understand first job dimensions, which are complex and interrelated in nature. That's why he mentioned the common dimensions of job satisfaction as work, pay, promotions, working conditions, co-workers.

- i) **The work itself:** The dimension describes employees' moods on their job, whether it has meaning or a purpose, or if the work is enjoyable. According to Landy (1989), employees who are committed in a work that they find interesting, that work is likely to contribute to job satisfaction.
- ii) **Pay:** The dimension relates to how fairly employees are paid for their work, length of time and chances of salary increments, as well as how appreciated the employees may feel by the salary received from the organization. According to Luthans (1998), the salary not only helps employees to satisfy their basic needs, but is also important in satisfying the higher level need of employees.
- iii) **Supervision:** The dimension describes whether a supervisor is fair, like employers show an interest for employee's feelings and competency of performance of managerial duties. According to (Ting, 1997) employees are likely high levels of job satisfaction if supervisors provide them with support and corporation in completing their tasks.
- iv) **Promotion:** The dimension relates to opportunities for advancement, employees being promoted fairly for a work well done and how they can be promoted compared to other organizations. For Landy (1989), each opportunity employees can have to be promoted is also likely to spread an influence on job satisfaction.
- v) **Co-worker:** The dimension describes whether employees like or enjoy company of other people he/she works with. According to Mowday & Sutton (1993), when the relationship is at a good level, it will increase the level of satisfaction in work.
- vi) **Working condition:** The dimension describes whether the environment of employees is good or not. A positive work environment is essential for employee's mental and physical well-being. According to Luthans (1998), if employees work in a clean, friendly environment, they will find it easier to come to work.

2.2 Organizational commitment

The concept organizational commitment has grown in popularity in the literature on industrial and organizational psychology. Early studies on organizational commitment viewed the concept as a single dimension, based on an attitudinal perspective, embracing identification, involvement and loyalty (Porter, Steers, Mowday & Boulian, 1974). Organizational commitment is defined as an individual's psychological bond to the organisation, including a sense of job involvement, loyalty and belief in the values of the organisation. O'Reilly (1989).

2.2.1 Components of Organizational commitment

The most used model in organizational commitment was developed by (Meyer and Allen, 1997) who used the tri-dimensional model to analyze organizational commitment in three dimensions which are: affective, continuance and normative commitments. Those dimensions explain how organizational commitment development look like and how strong the employee's behavior is.

- i) **Affective commitment:** The first dimension of organizational commitment represents the emotion of attachment of employees to the organisation they are working for. According to Meyer and Allen (1997). Affective commitment is the employee's emotional attachment to, identification with, and involvement in the organisation.
- ii) **Continuance commitment:** The second dimension of the tri-dimensional model of organizational commitment represents the awareness of the results associated with leaving the organisation. It is reflective in nature because of how employees take risk associated with leaving the organization that they are working currently.
- iii) **Normative commitment:** The last dimension of the organizational commitment model according to Meyer and Allen (1997) talks about obligations feelings to remain as an employee in the organization that you are working for. According to Meyer and Allen (1991) employees with normative commitment feel that they

should remain with the organisation.

2.2.2 Understanding Organizational commitment theories

- i) The side-bet theory: Becker (1960) proposed that: commitments come into being when a person, by making a side bet, links extraneous interests with a consistent line of activity. So, the effect of making side bets is to raise the cost of failing to persist in a course of action. In the case of organizational commitment, the course of action is staying with the company. Side bets can take various forms, but Becker suggested that they fall into several broad categories: generalized cultural expectations about responsible behavior, self-presentation concerns, impersonal bureaucratic arrangements, and individual adjustments to social positions, and non-work concerns.
- ii) Social cognitive theory: Social Cognitive theory from Albert Bandura, point out how cognitive, behavioral, personal, and environmental factors converse to determine motivation and behavior (Crothers, Hughes, & Morine, 2008). According to him, human functioning is the result of the interaction among all three of these factors (Crothers et al., 2008), as include in his Triadic Reciprocal Determinism model (Wood & Bandura, 1989). While it may appear that one factor is lead reason, there are numerous factors that play a role in human behavior. After all, the influencing factors are not of equal strength, nor do they all occur concurrently (Wood & Bandura, 1989).
- iii) Social exchange theory: Social exchange theory is related on a central premise: which means the exchange of social and material resources is a fundamental form of human interaction. Some theories developed in neoclassical economics, cultural anthropology and psychology, states that thoughts on social exchange compress on how interaction patterns are molded by power relationships between individuals, and the resulting efforts to achieve balance in exchange relations.

3. Research Method

3.1 Establishing Organizational Commitment Model

By establishing the commitment model for employee this research has classified the commitment factors into three big factors, described as follow: Team work, Job and Organization. Second the same model will be separated into three by giving each factors mentioned two factors like: Team work (supervisor and goal setting), job (responsibility and motivation) and organization (culture and Benefits). Third supervisor (Supervision, cohesion or Good relationship and Fair treatment). Goal setting (Success, cooperation and suggestion). Responsibility (Leadership, quality of work and trust). Motivation (Effort, working condition and coworker attitude). Culture (Transparency and behavior norms). Benefits (Rewards, promotion and salary).

Figure 1: Main Organizational Commitment Model

3.2 Relationship between Organizational Commitment and Job Satisfaction

Organizational commitment and job satisfaction of the employees have always been the interest of many researchers in management fields and many other fields, due to the fact that they are defined as the main determinants of the efficiency of a company (Allen & Meyer, 1996, Lau & Chong, 2002). Organizational

commitment has a positive influence on job satisfaction, which in turn will affect the turnover intention (Bateman & Strasser 1984). According to (Lau & Chong 2002) when employees are highly committed to the organizations, they may experience higher levels of job satisfaction. The only difference between the two concepts is that while organizational commitment can be defined as the emotional responses which an employee has towards his organization; job satisfaction is the responses that an employee has towards any job. (Kacmar & Brymer 1999) even point out in their research that the two concepts are related and have a relationship in a positive way. Akar and Yildirim (2008) went deeper and found out a positive correlation with affective, continuance and normative commitment.

The 17 last factors mentioned will be used in the questionnaire for survey in China and in Congo Brazzaville. They are separated into 43 questions explained as follow:

- i) **Supervision:** One of the two high priorities that a good supervisor put in application are coaching and supervising employees. When employees are well coached and supervised, the action plans and time lines will be clearly established as well. The supervisor dispatches and also provides ongoing guidance and support to the employee as they complete their action plans.
- ii) **Cohesion or Good Relationship:** The supervisor is the first person to bring among employees of the team the cohesion, the unification which will increase the likelihood of employee satisfaction and will serve as an incentive for employees to arrive prepared and willing to conquer the tasks given. Because Lack of cohesion within the group is certain to result in unnecessary stress, tension and distances among coworkers that will make the work to suffer.
- iii) **Fair Treatment:** Usually a good supervisor understands the organization and the employee's task better than the employee. Consequently, that good supervisor is in a unique position to give good advice to the employee about job and career. The employee can take the supervisor who gives him a fair treatment as a model for direction and development.
- iv) **Success:** One measure of group effectiveness is how well a group accomplishes its goals. Studies have shown that the worst thing you can do for group to perform well is not to set specific goals. Even easy, specific goals are better for employees working together in a group than nonspecific goals.
- v) **Cooperation:** It is a must for the employees to appreciate and understand that the working group is planed to be a forum for cooperation and participation. All member of the group represents an asset, so the cooperation will not only motivate but also fill the empty place that delays the work. Maintaining and strengthening communication lines with all parties involved in the group is essential for each and every one to be more committed.
- vi) **Suggestion:** For any work groups, participants will be more committed to the goal set if they can suggest something they think it's right for the progress of the tasks given but when it's not the case it will reduce less and less the motivation, participants will be working just for the sake of not being reprimand.
- vii) **Leadership:** Employees who have been given leadership into their organization and take it as responsibilities not as power always make sure to become a model in their work place. That responsibility given helps themselves and others to do the right things. By setting direction, building an inspiring vision, and creating something new, those leader have more commitment, they have the sense of belonging of that organization they are working for.
- viii) **Quality of Work:** is also an important factor for improving job satisfaction and one of the most important parts that it plays is determining the overall well-being of the organization.
- ix) **Trust:** When employees are given the trust that they really deserve, it will build a strong commitment, respect and loyalty, as well as a supportive and safe work environment. Because distrust will just increase tension and negative "on guard" behavior, which can erode the spirit of the Organization.
- x) **Effort:** For employees, it's just having interest, in the work that they are assigned to. They will be willing to put in additional effort which will make a company to go forward.
- xi) **Working Condition:** A positive work environment is essential for employee's mental and physical well-being. Good working conditions arise from values that the company views as important to its mission, such as ensuring a manageable workload and that increases commitment to employees.
- xii) **Coworker Attitude:** When people you are working with are having a good, positive attitude, along with positive thinking around you, will reflect on what you do and make you a more productive employee. This can determine how committed you get to your projects and also how you will be perceived by others.

- xiii) **Transparency:** Transparency in the workplace can increase employee productivity and happiness and can reduce turnover, that's why some companies have opted for that transparency which foster a culture of trust between leaders and their employees. In that case of transparency, employees understand their role in the purpose of the company, put their trust in their employer which give them more commitment.
- xiv) **Behavior Norms:** There are some rules that an organization uses to define its good and bad values, beliefs, attitudes and behaviors. They are so important that if any employees fail to stick to the rules can result in severe punishment and make them less committed. The most feared of which is exclusion from the organization.
- xv) **Reward:** Several researches have indicated that providing rewards for goal attainment can increase effort and strengthen individuals' goal commitment, which can result in better performance. Those rewards have been required to ensure that the contribution of employees in an organization is recognized by both non-financial and financial means.
- xvi) **Promotion:** It's just when an employee passes a process through the organization whereby he's given a higher share of duty, because the organization thinks that it is time to add more responsibilities or a way to keep him on continuing to perform well. That process is not just beneficial for employees but is also crucial for the organization; it boosts the morale of promoted employees, increases their productivity and hence improves upon the overall profits earned by the organization.
- xvii) **Salary:** Several scientific studies have found that individuals who have a high overall satisfaction with regard to their use are those that demonstrate the highest level of organizational commitment, satisfaction and this is based on several aspects, which salary is part.

4. Data Analysis Method

For this research, we used IBM SPSS Statistics 21 that has been our method for statistical analysis data. SPSS Statistics is a software package for managing data and calculating a wide variety of statistics. The software, long produced by SPSS Inc around 1975, has been released as a first version in 1968 as statistical package for the social science by (Nie, Bent & Hull) then acquired by IBM in 2009. Now SPSS is a widely used program for statistical analysis in social science, it is also used by market researchers, health researchers, survey companies, government, education researchers, marketing organizations, data miners and others. In addition to statistical analysis, data management (case selection, file reshaping, creating derived data) and data documentation (a metadata dictionary was stored in the data file) are features of the base software.

5. Descriptive Statistics and Results

In this research that aimed to compare organizational commitment on job satisfaction between China and Congo Brazzaville, we managed to make a questionnaire based survey, to get data. 380 questionnaires were set, whose 190 each has been shared in both countries. In Congo most of the survey was questionnaire form, 146 feedbacks was collected after three months of the whole survey process and in China 164 feedbacks was collected from only questionnaire forms. The survey was set mostly in some companies based in Nanjing, Hefei, Zhenzhiang, Yangzhou and other companies around Jiangsu province. The results was presented as follow: First part, the comparison on the general information between both countries and the second one, the comparison on the 17 sub-factors listed above and which took place into the questionnaire.

- i) **Gender:** On the 190 questionnaires shared, 84 and 62 responded which are male and female respectively 57.5% and 42.5%. Male respondents were much willing to help than female, which quiet explain the number of male working in Congo than female. While in China 27 and 137 of 164 respondents are male and female, respectively like 16.5% and 83.5%. According to the survey in Congo the gender is not that large compared to China where the population is very big and the number of women working.
- ii) **Age:** According to the survey quiet 50% of respondents in Congo are more than 32 years old, compared to China where nearly 60% of respondents are less than 32 years old due to the large number of youth graduated. The problem is more on the Congo's side where most of the representatives are not that young.
- iii) **Marital Status:** According to the survey less of 30% of respondents in Congo are married and those who are, are more than 33 years old while in China quiet 40% of them are married and they are in the average between 29-33 years old.
- iv) **Education:** The survey points out that 60.5% of the respondents in Congo have a level of undergraduate of all among other degrees. But in the China 80% of respondents have a level of postgraduate.

- v) **Jobs:** Due to difficulties faced in public organizations, which one of them was to get a notice first so that you can be allowed to carry out data to make a survey, it was difficult to get, that's why the survey was mainly based on private organizations. For China and Congo 96% and 90.5% respectively most of respondents are private officer. This survey may show some lack since it may not have access to all parts.
- vi) **Work Experience:** For Congo less than 5 years of work experience made the survey to 60.3%, next between 5-10 years the survey got 17%, 10-15 years the survey got 7%, 15-20 years the survey got 10.5% and more than 20 years the survey got 5.2%. 45.9% of Chinese respondents have less than 5 years work experience due to the fact that they start working on time and work frequently. 5-10 years made the survey to 40%, that's proving ones more that the education is higher than in Congo.
- vii) **Position Classification:** About the position classification, the survey have pointed out some varieties, 55. % of respondents in Congo is working in different field such as: CEO, manager, accountant, finance, etc ... while in China 61.5% of respondents is in human resources position.

Table 1: New Model of Organizational commitment Factors between China and Congo Brazzaville	
CHINA	CONGO-Brazzaville
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Success • Salary • Promotion • Trust • Leadership • Coworker attitude • Rewards • Supervision • Cohesion or Good relationship • Effort • Fair treatment • Cooperation • Quality of work • Suggestion • Work condition • Transparency • Behavior norms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Salary • Leadership • Promotion • Rewards • Supervision • Suggestion • Fair treatment • Cohesion or Good relationship • Cooperation • Effort • Coworker attitude • Success • Trust • Quality of work • Work condition • Behavior norms • Transparency

As we can see from this new model of Organizational commitment Subtracted into the seventeen factors of commitment proposed, one can notice the highest factor that responders on the Chinese side has focused is success and on the other side in Congo the highest factors is salary due to level of life in the country. This can also demonstrate the differentiation in culture and choices made in both countries.

The choice of Chinese rely on the fact that after making long studies it's better to be in an organization that set specific goals which in return may match with their study level so that they can progress in their respective career. There is no way for them to be involved in any low level of organization if they know they have a big potential.

Chinese like big challenges, they are hard working; they usually make sure to please their superior, which guarantee their post, salary, promotion, trust and other factors for their own success.

Most responders in Congo have focused on salary as motivation factors to get to job satisfaction. One of the reasons why they focused on that is simply the fact of difficulties that people meet. There is decadence on the standard of living, there is the rich and poor, the average class is scarcely distinguishable. People show their level of

commitment once they know they have enough to survive, they make sure to keep that level of commitment to get more responsibilities, promotions and other factors, which for sure come with additional remuneration.

6. Conclusion

This study analyzes the impact that Organizational commitment can have on job satisfaction between China and Congo. We can notice that the lowest factor that Chinese responders have pointed out is behavior norms, which is totally different from the responders in Congo. That showed in the side of China that there are more important factors that they value most to get them more committed and being satisfied, that doesn't exclude the importance of behavior norms, but comes late in their point of view, as we all know norms are everywhere, and without even paying attention, people follow them most of the time and they help to build feelings of security and also bring orientation in the organization. On the side of Congo, transparency comes at the end as factors of commitment to get on job satisfaction, even when we know that it plays a critical role in any organization as fostering a culture of trust between leaders and their employees, the opposite leads to a discontent which questions the actions of the organization.

Despite that difference as lowest factors, we can notice that top factors of commitment are practically noted the same, if it's not one factor valuable in one side and also valuable in other side but with some margin of other factors to show the differences. Factors like promotion, leadership, rewards, etc.... show how important they are in both countries in way to have a positive influence on job satisfaction. At the end despite the standard of living, education and differences in culture, organizational commitment is stronger in China than in Congo.

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